

Supplementary files of chapter 6 Mebeverine and the influence of labeling in adolescents with irritable bowel syndrome or functional abdominal pain-NOS: a 2x2 randomized, placebo-controlled trial.

Supplementary figures

Supplementary figure 1. Randomization scheme

Supplementary figure 2. Proportion of patients with treatment success at T2 after treatment for all treatment groups with odds ratios (95% confidence interval).

Supplementary figure 3. Proportion of patients with adequate relief at T2 after treatment for all treatment groups with odds ratios (95% confidence interval).

Supplementary figure 4. Mean abdominal pain intensity scores. Figure S4A: mebeverine vs. placebo. Figure S4B: mebeverine label vs. blinded trial label.

Supplementary figure 5. Mean abdominal pain frequency scores. Figure S5A: mebeverine vs. placebo. Figure S5B: mebeverine label vs. blinded trial label.

Supplementary tables**Supplementary table 1.** Overview of endpoints

Endpoint	Instrument	T0	T1 4 weeks after start treatment	T2 End of treatment	T3 4 weeks follow-up
Abdominal pain	Abdominal pain diaries	X	X	X	X
Associated symptoms	Abdominal pain diaries	X	X	X	X
Defecation frequency	Abdominal pain diaries	X	X	X	X
School absence	Abdominal pain diaries	X	X	X	X
Use of pain medication	Abdominal pain diaries	X	X	X	X
Adequate relief	Binary question on adequate relief			X	
Depression and anxiety	Revised Child Anxiety and Depression Scale-short version (RCADS-25) ¹	X		X	
Quality of life	Pediatric Quality of Life (PedsQL 4.0) ²	X		X	
Somatization symptoms	Children's Somatization Inventory (CSI) ³	X		X	

Supplementary table 2. Logistic regression analysis to identify factors predicting treatment success at T2.

Predictor*	Simple logistic regression		Multiple logistic regression	
	OR (95% CI)	P-value	OR (95% CI)	P-value
Sex (male vs female)	1.62 (0.88 – 2.98)	0.12	1.19 (0.61 – 2.31)	0.62
Age at inclusion (in years)	0.87 (0.72 – 1.04)	0.12	0.89 (0.73 – 1.08)	0.23
First-line family member with FAPD	1.10 (0.59 – 2.07)	0.76		
Diagnosis (IBS vs. FAP-NOS)	1.27 (0.67 – 2.40)	0.46		
Duration of symptoms (in years) Including center (academic vs teaching center)	1.06 (0.99 – 1.14)	0.08	1.08 (1.00 – 1.16)	0.06
Abdominal pain intensity at baseline	1.55 (0.86 – 2.81)	0.15	1.36 (0.71 – 2.58)	0.36
Abdominal pain frequency at baseline (hours)	0.80 (0.58 – 1.10)	0.16		
Abdominal pain frequency at baseline (hours)	0.99 (0.94 – 1.04)	0.54		
Total quality of life (PedsQL 4.0)	1.01 (0.97 – 1.04)	0.68		
Anxiety scores (RCADS-25)	0.97 (0.93 – 1.02)	0.22		
Depression scores (RCADS-25)	0.94 (0.82 – 1.09)	0.43		
Somatization symptoms (CSI)	0.99 (0.97 – 1.01)	0.39		
Compliance to study treatment	0.93 (0.50 – 1.71)	0.81		
Educational degree mother				
High (ref)				
Middle	0.82 (0.41 – 1.67)	0.59		
Low	1.14 (0.53 – 2.46)	0.74		
Educational degree father				
High (ref)				
Middle	1.32 (0.71 – 2.43)	0.38		
Low	1.33 (0.73 – 2.41)	0.36		
Mebeverine vs. placebo	1.08 (0.59 – 1.99)	0.81		
Mebeverine label vs. Blinded trial label	2.84 (1.52 – 5.34)	0.001	2.95 (1.52 – 5.73)	0.001
* For continuous predictors, the OR should be interpreted as the change in OR with one unit increase in the predictor value.				

Supplementary table 3. Logistic regression analysis to identify factors predicting adequate relief at T2.

Predictor*	Simple logistic regression		Multiple logistic regression	
	OR (95% CI)	P-value	OR (95% CI)	P-value
Sex (male vs. female)	1.54 (0.92 – 2.59)	0.10	1.12 (0.60 – 2.10)	0.72
Age at inclusion (In years)	0.92 (0.80 – 1.07)	0.27		
Diagnosis (IBS vs. FAP-NOS)	1.05 (0.63 – 1.74)	0.86		
Duration of symptoms (In years)	1.02 (0.96 – 1.08)	0.57		
Including centre (Academic vs teaching centre)	1.08 (0.67 – 1.76)	0.75		
Abdominal pain intensity at baseline	0.66 (0.50 – 0.87)	0.003	0.67 (0.48 – 0.92)	0.02
Abdominal pain frequency at baseline (hours)	0.98 (0.95 – 1.02)	0.41		
Total quality of life at baseline (PedsQL 4.0)	1.02 (0.99 – 1.05)	0.16	1.00 (0.96 – 1.03)	0.82
Anxiety scores at baseline (RCADS-25)	0.96 (0.93 – 1.00)	0.03	0.97 (0.92 – 1.01)	0.15
Depression scores (RCADS-25)	0.96 (0.87 – 1.07)	0.48		
Somatization symptoms at baseline (CSI)	0.99 (0.97 – 1.00)	0.11	1.0 (0.98 – 1.02)	0.92
Compliance to study treatment	1.00 (0.99 – 1.01)	0.95		
Educational degree mother				
High (ref)				
Middle	0.93 (0.53 – 1.65)	0.81		
Low	0.93 (0.53 – 1.65)	0.93		
Educational degree father				
High (ref)				
Middle	0.82 (0.42 – 1.63)	0.57		
Low	1.23 (0.57 – 2.62)	0.60		
Mebeverine vs. placebo	0.83 (0.51 – 1.35)	0.46		
Mebeverine label vs. blinded trial label	1.78 (1.09 – 2.90)	0.02	1.71 (0.97 – 3.03)	0.06

*** For continuous predictors, the OR should be interpreted as the change in OR with one unit increase in the predictor value.**

Supplementary table 4. Increase in abdominal pain scores during follow-up of patients who stopped study treatment due to adequate relief at T2 after treatment with placebo or mebeverine.

	Placebo (N = 61)	Mebeverine (N = 54)	P-value
Daily intensity score, mean (SD)¶	0.7 (1.2)	0.7 (1.3)	0.13 [†]
Daily frequency, hours, mean (SD)	3.4 (6.8)	2.5 (6.2)	0.03 [†]

¶ Abdominal pain intensity was scored on a scale from 0 to 5, with 0 indicating no pain and 5 the worst imaginable pain.

† By one-way analysis of variance.

Supplementary table 5. Increase in abdominal pain scores during follow-up of patients who stopped study treatment due to adequate relief at T2 after treatment labelled as mebeverine or blinded trial medication.

	Mebeverine label (N = 61)	Blinded trial label (N = 54)	P-value
Daily intensity score, mean (SD)¶	0.8 (1.2)	0.5 (1.2)	0.004†
Daily frequency, hours, mean (SD)	3.1 (5.7)	2.8 (7.5)	0.10†

¶ Abdominal pain intensity was scored on a scale from 0 to 5, with 0 indicating no pain and 5 the worst imaginable pain.

† By one-way analysis of variance.

Supplementary table 6. Responders in terms of abdominal pain intensity, frequency or both (i.e. treatment success) at T1, T2, and T3 after treatment with placebo or mebeverine.

	Placebo (N = 134)	Mebeverine (N = 134)	P-value
Treatment success, frequency (%)			
T1	17 (12.7)	10 (7.5)	.86
T2	30 (22.0)	31 (23.4)	.81
T3	14 (10.4)	18 (13.4)	.51
>50% reduction of abdominal pain intensity, frequency (%)			
T1	22 (16.4)	15 (11.2)	.27
T2	35 (26.1)	39 (29.1)	.62
T3	23 (17.2)	30 (22.0)	.27
>50% reduction of abdominal pain frequency in hours, frequency (%)			
T1	31 (23.1)	23 (17.2)	.27
T2	42 (32.9)	38 (23.4)	.61
T3	25 (18.7)	24 (17.9)	.92

† By one-way analysis of variance.

Supplementary table 7. Responders in terms of abdominal pain intensity, frequency or both (i.e. treatment success) at T1, T2, and T3 after treatment labelled as mebeverine or blinded trial medication.

	Mebeverine label (N = 133)	Blinded trial label (N = 135)	P-value
Treatment success, frequency (%)			
T1	16 (12.0)	11 (8.1)	.36
T2	42 (31.6)	19 (14.1)	.001
T3	21 (15.8)	12 (8.9)	.11
>50% reduction of abdominal pain intensity, frequency (%)			
T1	22 (16.5)	15 (11.1)	.22
T2	50 (37.6)	24 (17.8)	<.001
T3	35 (26.3)	18 (13.3)	.02
>50% reduction of abdominal pain frequency, frequency (%)			
T1	29 (21.8)	25 (18.5)	.47
T2	52 (39.1)	28 (20.7)	.003
T3	27 (20.3)	21 (15.6)	.32

† By one-way analysis of variance.

Supplementary table 8. Responders in terms of abdominal pain intensity, frequency or both (i.e. treatment success) at T1, T2, and T3 after all four treatment groups.

	Mebeverine with blinded trial label (N= 68)	Mebeverine with mebeverine label (N = 66)	Placebo with blinded trial label (N = 67)	Placebo with mebeverine label (N= 67)
Treatment success, frequency (%)				
T1	4 (5.9)	6 (9.1)	8 (11.9)	10 (14.9)
T2	7 (10.3)	24 (36.4)	12 (17.6)	18 (26.4)
T3	6 (8.8)	12 (18.2)	6 (9.0)	9 (13.4)
>50% reduction of abdominal pain intensity, frequency (%)				
T1	7 (10.3)	9 (13.6)	9 (13.4)	14 (20.9)
T2	10 (14.7)	30 (45.5)	16 (23.9)	24 (35.8)
T3	9 (13.2)	21 (31.8)	8 (11.9)	14 (20.9)
>50% reduction of abdominal pain frequency, frequency (%)				
T1	11 (16.2)	12 (18.2)	14 (20.9)	17 (25.4)
T2	11 (16.2)	27 (40.9)	18 (26.9)	25 (37.3)
T3	10 (14.7)	13 (19.7)	11 (16.4)	14 (20.9)

† By one-way analysis of variance.

Supplementary table 9. Secondary endpoints during treatment and follow-up for placebo vs. mebeverine.

	Placebo (N = 134)	Mebeverine (N = 134)
Total quality of life (PedsQL 4.0), mean (SD) \bar{x}		
T0	75.8 (10.6) N = 107	76.4 (9.6) N = 110
T2	78.0 (11.1) N = 78	79.2 (9.9) N = 81
Physical quality of life (PedsQL 4.0), mean (SD) \bar{x}		
T0	79.1 (11.7) N = 107	80.1 (10.4) N = 110
T2	80.7 (12.1) N = 78	83.2 (10.6) N = 81
Psychosocial quality of life (PedsQL 4.0), mean (SD) \bar{x}		
T0	74.0 (11.8) N = 106	74.3 (11.1) N = 110
T2	76.8 (12.2) N = 78	77.4 (11.5) N = 81
Anxiety (RCADS-25), mean (SD) \bar{x}		
T0	10.2 (1.6) N = 109	10.6 (1.7) N = 111
T2	9.7 (1.9) N = 81	11.0 (1.6) N = 81
Depression (RCADS-25), mean (SD) \bar{x}		
T0	4.2 (2.7) N = 109	3.9 (2.5) N = 111
T2	3.9 (2.7) N = 81	3.9 (2.6) N = 81
Somatization: non-GI- symptoms (CSI), mean (SD) \bar{x}.		
T0	29.4 (17.1) N = 108	27.5 (14.7) N = 111
T2	24.3 (15.9) N = 80	26.4 (16.4) N = 81
Defecation frequency per day, median (IQR)		
T0	3.1 (2.1 – 4.4)	3.2 (2.1 – 4.2)
T1	3.0 (2.1 – 4.0)	3.3 (2.2 – 4.2)
T2	2.9 (2.0 – 4.3)	2.8 (1.9 – 4.4)

T3	2.8 (2.2 – 3.4)	2.9 (2.2 – 3.6)
Stool consistency, mean (SD) †		
T0	4.1 (0.2)	4.0 (0.2)
T1	4.4 (0.2)	4.3 (0.2)
T2	4.0 (0.2)	4.0 (0.2)
T3	3.8 (0.3)	3.8 (0.2)
Use of painkillers, days, median (IQR) ‡		
T0	0.4 (0.0 – 1.4)	0.2 (0.0 – 1.0)
T1	0.6 (0.0 – 1.6)	0.7 (0.0 – 1.6)
T2	0.2 (0.0 – 1.4)	0.1 (0.0 – 1.4)
T3	0.8 (0.0 – 1.7)	0.7 (0.0 – 1.6)
School absence, days, median (IQR) §		
T0	0.4 (0.0 – 1.5)	0.3 (0.0 – 1.4)
T1	0.2 (0.0 – 1.4)	0.5 (0.0 – 1.4)
T2	0.4 (0.0 – 1.6)	0.3 (0.0 – 1.6)
T3	1.0 (0.0 – 1.9)	0.7 (0.0 – 1.7)
Nausea, severity, median (IQR) ¶		
T0	1.9 (0.5 – 3.1)	1.5 (0.5 – 3.3)
T1	1.1 (0.4 – 1.9)	1.2 (0.2 – 2.2)
T2	0.8 (0.0 – 1.9)	1.0 (0.0 – 2.1)
T3	1.2 (0.4 – 1.8)	1.2 (0.2 – 1.8)
Headache, severity, median (IQR) ¶		
T0	2.0 (0.6 – 3.5)	1.8 (0.4 – 3.2)
T1	1.1 (0.1 – 2.2)	1.6 (0.6 – 2.5)
T2	0.9 (0.0 – 2.0)	0.9 (0.0 – 2.2)
T3	1.2 (0.4 – 1.8)	1.1 (0.2 – 1.8)
Loss of appetite, severity, median (IQR) ¶		
T0	0.9 (0.0 – 2.3)	0.9 (0.0 – 2.5)
T1	0.8 (0.0 – 1.6)	1.0 (0.0 – 1.8)
T2	0.5 (0.0 – 1.2)	0.7 (0.0 – 1.4)
T3	1.0 (0.0 – 1.7)	0.9 (0.0 – 1.6)

† Quality of life scores were scored on a scale from 0 to 100, with 0 indicating worst quality of life and 100 the best quality of life.

‡ Anxiety was scored on a scale from 0 to 60, with 0 indicating lowest severity of anxiety and 60 the most severe anxiety.

§ Depression was scored on a scale from 0 to 15, with 0 indicating lowest severity of depression and 15 the highest severity of depression.

† Stool consistency was assessed with the use of the Bristol Stool Form Scale, which ranges from 1 to 7, with 1 indicating hard stool and 7 indicating watery diarrhea

§ Somatization was scored on a scale from 0 to 140, with 0 indicating lowest somatization and 140 the highest somatization.

¶ Use of painkillers was scored as the number of days of that week that the patient took a painkiller.

¶ School absence was scored as the number of days of that week that the patient was absent from school.

¶ Nausea, headache and loss of appetite were scored on a scale from 0 to 10, with 0 indicating no nausea, headache, or loss of appetite and 10 the highest severity of these symptoms.

Supplementary table 10. Secondary endpoints during treatment and follow-up for treatment with mebeverine label vs. treatment with blinded trial label.

	Mebeverine label (N = 133)	Blinded trial label (N = 135)
Total quality of life (PedsQL 4.0), mean (SD) \bar{x}		
T0	76.0 (9.6) N = 103	76.2 (10.6) N = 114
T2	78.3 (10.5) N = 76	78.9 (10.6) N = 83
Physical quality of life (PedsQL 4.0), mean (SD) \bar{x}		
T0	80.4 (10.8) N = 103	79.7 (11.3) N = 114
T2	82.2 (11.4) N = 76	81.7 (11.5) N = 83
Psychosocial quality of life (PedsQL 4.0), mean (SD) \bar{x}		
T0	73.7 (11.0) N = 102	74.6 (11.9) N = 114
T2	76.5 (12.1) N = 76	77.6 (11.7) N = 83
Anxiety (RCADS-25), mean (SD) \bar{x}		
T0	11.1 (1.7) N = 105	9.8 (1.7) N = 115
T2	11.2 (1.9) N = 77	9.5 (1.6) N = 85
Depression (RCADS-25), mean (SD) \bar{x}		
T0	4.1 (2.6) N = 105	4.0 (2.6) N = 115
T2	4.1 (2.8) N = 77	3.7 (2.5) N = 85
Somatization: non-GI- symptoms (CSI), mean (SD) \bar{x}		
T0	29.2 (16.2) N = 104	27.7 (16.2) N = 115
T2	25.6 (17.1) N = 76	25.1 (15.4) N = 85
Defecation frequency per day, median (IQR)		
T0	2.8 (1.9 – 4.0)	3.3 (2.3 – 4.7)
T1	3.2 (2.3 – 4.0)	3.2 (2.1 – 4.2)

T2	2.7 (1.8 – 4.1)	3.1 (2.0 – 4.4)
T3	2.8 (2.1 – 3.5)	2.8 (2.2 – 3.5)
Stool consistency, mean (SD) †		
T0	4.1 (0.2)	4.0 (0.2)
T1	4.4 (0.2)	4.3 (0.2)
T2	4.0 (0.3)	4.0 (0.2)
T3	3.8 (0.2)	3.8 (0.2)
Use of painkillers, days, median (IQR) ‡		
T0	0.1 (0.0 – 1.1)	0.4 (0.0 – 1.3)
T1	0.6 (0.0 – 1.5)	0.6 (0.0 – 1.6)
T2	0.2 (0.0 – 1.6)	0.1 (0.0 – 1.3)
T3	0.7 (0.0 – 1.6)	0.8 (0.0 – 1.7)
School absence, days, median (IQR) §		
T0	0.4 (0.0 – 1.5)	0.3 (0.0 – 1.5)
T1	0.2 (0.0 – 1.4)	0.4 (0.0 – 1.3)
T2	0.5 (0.0 – 1.7)	0.2 (0.0 – 1.4)
T3	0.7 (0.0 – 1.6)	1.0 (0.0 – 1.9)
Nausea, severity, median (IQR) ¶		
T0	1.6 (0.6 – 3.2)	1.8 (0.5 – 3.3)
T1	1.1 (0.3 – 2.2)	1.2 (0.2 – 1.9)
T2	1.1 (0.0 – 2.0)	0.7 (0.0 – 1.8)
T3	1.3 (0.4 – 1.9)	1.1 (0.3 – 1.7)
Headache, severity, median (IQR) ¶		
T0	2.0 (0.5 – 3.2)	2.0 (0.4 – 3.6)
T1	1.4 (0.5 – 2.5)	1.3 (0.3 – 2.2)
T2	1.0 (0.0 – 2.1)	0.9 (0.0 – 2.1)
T3	1.1 (0.3 – 1.8)	1.2 (0.4 – 1.9)
Loss of appetite, severity, median (IQR) ¶		
T0	0.8 (0.0 – 2.4)	1.0 (0.0 – 2.5)
T1	0.9 (0.0 – 1.7)	0.9 (0.0 – 1.7)
T2	0.6 (0.0 – 1.2)	0.6 (0.0 – 1.4)
T3	0.9 (0.0 – 1.5)	1.0 (0.0 – 1.7)

† Quality of life scores were scored on a scale from 0 to 100, with 0 indicating worst quality of life and 100 the best quality of life.

‡ Anxiety was scored on a scale from 0 to 60, with 0 indicating lowest severity of anxiety and 60 the most severe anxiety.

§ Depression was scored on a scale from 0 to 15, with 0 indicating lowest severity of depression and 15 the highest severity of depression.

¶ Somatization was scored on a scale from 0 to 140, with 0 indicating lowest somatization and 140 the highest somatization.

‡ Use of painkillers was scored as the number of days of that week that the patient took a painkiller.

§ School absence was scored as the number of days of that week that the patient was absent from school.

¶ Nausea, headache and loss of appetite were scored on a scale from 0 to 10, with 0 indicating no nausea, headache, or loss of appetite and 10 the highest severity of these symptoms.

Supplementary table 11. Secondary endpoints during treatment and follow-up for all four treatment groups.

Secondary endpoints	Mebeverine with blinded trial label (N = 68)	Mebeverine with mebeverine label (N = 66)	Placebo with blinded trial label (N = 67)	Placebo with mebeverine label (N = 67)
Total quality of life (PedsQL 4.0), mean (SD) \bar{x}				
T0	77.1 (10.4) N = 59	75.23 (8.7) N = 50	75.2 (10.8) N = 55	76.5 (10.5) N = 52
T2	79.0 (10.3) N = 43	79.5 (10.5) N = 38	75.8 (11.0) N = 40	77.2 (11.4) N = 38
Physical quality of life (PedsQL 4.0), mean (SD) \bar{x}				
T0	80.9 (11.1) N = 59	80.9 (9.7) N = 51	78.4 (11.6) N = 55	79.8 (11.9) N = 52
T2	82.6 (10.6) N = 43	83.8 (10.6) N = 38	80.8 (12.4) N = 40	80.6 (10.7) N = 38
Psychosocial quality of life (PedsQL 4.0), mean (SD) \bar{x}				
T0	75.4 (11.7) N = 59	72.9 (10.3) N = 51	73.7 (12.0) N = 55	74.4 (11.8) N = 51
T2	77.4 (11.7) N = 43	77.1 (11.5) N = 38	77.8 (11.9) N = 40	75.6 (12.7) N = 38
Anxiety (RCADS-25), mean (SD) \bar{x}				
T0	10.0 (2.0) N = 59	11.4 (1.5) N = 52	9.6 (1.4) N = 56	10.8 (1.9) N = 53
T2	10.2 (1.5) N = 43	11.8 (1.8) N = 38	8.8 (1.7) N = 42	10.7 (2.0) N = 39
Somatization: non-GI-symptoms (CSI), mean (SD) \bar{x}				
T0	27.2 (14.9) N = 59	27.8 (14.6) N = 52	30.6 (17.6) N = 52	30.6 (17.6) N = 52
T2	25.9 (14.8) N = 43	27.0 (18.2) N = 38	24.1 (16.0) N = 38	24.1 (16.0) N = 38
Depression (RCADS-25), mean (SD) \bar{x}				
T0	4.0 (2.4)	3.8 (2.6)	4.1 (2.8)	4.3 (2.6)

	N = 59	N = 51	N = 56	N = 53
T2	3.7 (2.4)	4.0 (2.8)	3.6 (2.5)	4.3 (2.8)
	N = 43	N = 38	N = 42	N = 39
Defecation frequency per day, median (IQR)				
T0	3.1 (2.3 – 4.3)	3.1 (2.0 – 4.2)	3.5 (2.2 – 4.4)	2.6 (1.9 – 3.8)
T1	3.2 (2.0 – 4.4)	3.3 (2.5 – 4.1)	3.0 (2.1 – 4.0)	3.0 (2.2 – 4.0)
T2	2.9 (1.9 – 4.4)	2.8 (1.9 – 4.2)	3.4 (2.2 – 4.4)	2.7 (1.7 – 4.1)
T3	2.9 (2.3 – 3.6)	2.9 (2.2 – 3.6)	2.8 (2.2 – 3.4)	2.8 (2.1 – 3.4)
Stool consistency, mean (SD) †				
T0	4.0 (0.2)	4.0 (0.2)	4.0 (0.2)	4.1 (0.3)
T1	4.3 (0.2)	4.3 (0.2)	4.3 (0.2)	4.4 (0.2)
T2	4.0 (0.2)	4.0 (0.2)	4.0 (0.2)	4.0 (0.3)
T3	3.8 (0.2)	3.8 (0.2)	3.8 (0.2)	3.9 (0.3)
Use of painkillers, days, median (IQR) ††				
T0	0.5 (0.0 – 1.3)	0.0 (0.0 – 1.0)	0.4 (0.0 – 1.4)	0.4 (0.0 – 1.4)
T1	0.7 (0.0 – 1.5)	0.7 (0.0 – 1.8)	0.5 (0.0 – 1.6)	0.6 (0.0 – 1.5)
T2	0.1 (0.0 – 1.4)	0.2 (0.0 – 1.5)	0.1 (0.0 – 1.2)	0.3 (0.0 – 1.7)
T3	0.9 (0.0 – 1.8)	0.5 (0.0 – 1.5)	0.8 (0.0 – 1.7)	0.9 (0.0 – 1.7)
School absence, days, median (IQR) ††				
T0	0.3 (0.0 – 1.2)	0.4 (0.0 – 1.7)	0.4 (0.0 – 1.8)	0.3 (0.0 – 1.3)
T1	0.5 (0.0 – 1.2)	0.4 (0.0 – 1.5)	0.3 (0.0 – 1.5)	0.1 (0.0 – 1.3)
T2	0.2 (0.0 – 1.6)	0.5 (0.0 – 1.6)	0.3 (0.0 – 1.3)	0.5 (0.0 – 1.8)
T3	0.9 (0.0 – 1.9)	0.5 (0.0 – 1.5)	1.0 (0.0 – 2.0)	0.9 (0.0 – 1.8)
Nausea, severity, median (IQR) ††				
T0	1.8 (0.6 – 3.2)	1.4 (0.4 – 3.5)	1.5 (0.3 – 3.1)	2.1 (0.7 – 3.2)
T1	1.3 (0.3 – 2.8)	1.1 (0.1 – 1.9)	1.1 (0.4 – 1.9)	1.2 (0.4 – 1.9)
T2	1.2 (0.1 – 2.3)	0.8 (0.0 – 1.8)	1.0 (0.0 – 1.9)	0.6 (0.0 – 1.8)
T3	1.3 (0.4 – 2.0)	1.1 (0.1 – 1.7)	1.3 (0.4 – 1.9)	1.0 (0.4 – 1.7)
Headache, severity, median (IQR) ††				
T0	2.0 (0.4 – 3.7)	1.3 (0.5 – 3.1)	1.9 (0.5 – 3.4)	2.1 (0.6 – 3.6)
T1	1.6 (0.5 – 2.5)	1.5 (0.7 – 2.4)	1.1 (0.1 – 2.0)	1.3 (0.1 – 2.7)
T2	0.9 (0.0 – 2.5)	0.9 (0.0 – 2.1)	0.9 (0.0 – 2.0)	1.0 (0.0 – 2.1)
T3	1.2 (0.3 – 2.0)	1.0 (0.1 – 1.7)	1.2 (0.4 – 1.8)	1.2 (0.5 – 1.8)
Loss of appetite, severity, median (IQR) ††				
T0	1.2 (0.3 – 2.6)	0.7 (0.0 – 2.3)	1.0 (0.0 – 2.3)	0.9 (0.0 – 2.5)
T1	1.0 (0.1 – 2.1)	0.9 (0.0 – 1.7)	0.9 (0.0 – 1.5)	0.8 (0.0 – 1.7)
T2	0.8 (0.0 – 1.5)	0.6 (0.0 – 1.3)	0.4 (0.0 – 1.2)	0.6 (0.0 – 1.2)
T3	0.9 (0.0 – 1.7)	0.9 (0.0 – 1.5)	1.1 (0.0 – 1.8)	1.0 (0.1 – 1.5)

⌊ Quality of life scores were scored on a scale from 0 to 100, with 0 indicating worst quality of life and 100 the best quality of life.

⌋ Anxiety was scored on a scale from 0 to 60, with 0 indicating lowest severity of anxiety and 60 the most severe anxiety.

⌌ Depression was scored on a scale from 0 to 15, with 0 indicating lowest severity of depression and 15 the highest severity of depression.

⌍ Stool consistency was assessed with the use of the Bristol Stool Form Scale, which ranges from 1 to 7, with 1 indicating hard stool and 7 indicating watery diarrhea

⌎ Somatization was scored on a scale from 0 to 140, with 0 indicating lowest somatization and 140 the highest somatization.

⌏ Use of painkillers was scored as the number of days of that week that the patient took a painkiller.

⌐ School absence was scored as the number of days of that week that the patient was absent from school.

⌑ Nausea, headache and loss of appetite were scored on a scale from 0 to 10, with 0 indicating no nausea, headache, or loss of appetite and 10 the highest severity of these symptoms.

Supplementary appendices

Appendix S1.

Exclusion criteria

- Current treatment by another health care professional for abdominal symptoms
- Previous use of mebeverine
- Known hypersensitivity to the active substance or to any of the excipients ((magnesium stearate, polyacrylate dispersion, talc, Hypromellose, methacrylic acid – ethyl acrylate copolymer (1:1) dispersion, glycerol triacetate, gelatine, titanium dioxide (E171), shellac (E904), propylene glycol, ammonia solution (concentrated), potassium hydroxide, iron oxide black (E172)).
- Unintentional weight loss greater than or equal to 5% of their body weight within the last 3 months
- Gastrointestinal blood loss
- Recurrent or unexplained fevers
- Decreased growth velocity
- History of previous abdominal surgeries in the past 3 months
- Rome IV criteria diagnosis of functional constipation
- Children who tested positive for bacterial or parasites infections (window: 2 months before start study)
- Carbohydrate malabsorption diagnosed either clinically (2 weeks exclusion diet with resolution of symptoms) or with proper testing (breath test). Children with carbohydrate intolerance who continue to have IBS symptoms while on an exclusion diet can still be included.
- Significant chronic health condition requiring specialty care (e.g., lithiasis, ureteropelvic junction obstruction, sickle cell, cerebral palsy, hepatic, hematopoietic, renal, endocrine, or metabolic diseases) that could potentially impact the child's ability to participate or confound the results of the study.
- Known diagnosis of cystic fibrosis
- Known diagnosis of porphyria
- Known concomitant organic gastrointestinal disease.
- Current use of drugs which influence gastrointestinal motility, such as erythromycin, azithromycin, butyl scopolamine, domperidone, peppermint oil capsules, and Iberogast (current use of drugs which influence gastrointestinal motility may be met as long as the subject is on a stable dose and the dose will not be adjusted during the study.
- Insufficient knowledge of the Dutch language
- Pregnancy or current lactation. Women with childbearing potential must have a negative urine pregnancy test within 7 days prior to first dose of study treatment.

References

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3. Meesters C, Muris P, Ghys A, et al. The Children's Somatization Inventory: further evidence for its reliability and validity in a pediatric and a community sample of Dutch children and adolescents. *J Pediatr Psychol* 2003;28:413-22.